

MID-TERM DISSEMINATION, EXPLOITATION AND COMMUNICATION REPORT

D5.2

Fig. 01

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This document reports on the mid-term dissemination, exploitation and communication activities carried out in the PIE News project. The report accounts for the major changes that the communication identity of the project has undergone in order to respond to the multiple feedback provided through the participatory research activities conducted in the three pilot countries.

Research findings have brought an understanding of the communication activities as aiming at informing people, promoting collective meaning-making, and building relations so as to build an inclusive and empathic online and offline environment for people who cope with conditions of precariousness and risks of social exclusion and material deprivation. Research results have also emphasised the importance of building and leveraging the power of offline relations in order to foster engagement and the formation of a recursive public around the digital platform commonfare.net.

The document also provides a detailed account of the results of communication and dissemination work performed so far. Data and analytics are provided with regards to the project's institutional website, Facebook page, newsletter, factsheet, press releases, flyers, posters and stickers. An account of external events is also provided along with a plan of future networking events.

The conclusions highlight the organization of networking events and communication of bottom-up welfare good practices as the two main pillars on which to focus future public engagement activities.

European
Commission

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Fig. 02

Deliverable D5.2 reports on the mid-term dissemination, exploitation and communication strategies and activities envisioned and implemented in the PIE News project. These activities aim to achieve one of the main goals of the project, that is the formation of a recursive public around the value and practice of Commonfare. A recursive public is a social aggregate that will provide the project sustainability around a new model of welfare, based on the collective valorization of material and immaterial common goods (housing, work, healthcare, education, knowledge, art, culture, social relations, natural resources and public infrastructures), that is able to cope with the increasing level of job precarity, low income and risks of social exclusion across Europe.

Chapter 1 illustrates the role of public engagement in the PIE News project as a crucial component of the public design approach the project is pursuing and as key factor to ensure the sustainability of the commonfare.net digital platform. The chapter summarizes the reasons behind the decisions to revise the communication and dissemination strategy, starting from the very name of the project.

Chapter 2 explains the articulation of the communication strategy in PIE News according to three main trajectories: communication as informing, communication as meaning-making, communication as relation. Empirical examples from the project's communication are provided in order to clarify these three articulations. The chapter also provides a detailed report of the communication toolbox

the project has adopted, with data and analytics related to the performance of the project's institutional website, Facebook page, newsletter, factsheet, press releases, flyers, posters and stickers. Moreover, this chapter illustrates the plan regarding the communication and dissemination of bottom-up welfare good practices.

Chapter 3 discusses the importance of the organization of public events around the project, as they are considered essential to foster attachments based on commitment to the project and to promote the formation of relations that favour the emergence of a recursive public. An overview and analytics of external and networking events are provided in order to clarify and account for the strategy behind the organization of these events.

Chapter 4 provides a detailed account of the publications about the project produced so far. Publications are categorized according to the media formats, publics and goals they entail: peer-reviewed journals, magazines, e-journals, blogs, and project deliverables. The chapter includes an explanation of the goals and relations with the project with regards to each type of publication.

The conclusions build upon the reported communication and public engagement activities carried out so far to propose future steps to increase the visibility of the project and people's engagement, goals that rely upon the organization of PIE News Networking Events and on dissemination of bottom-up welfare good practices.

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ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	MEANING
BIN	Basic Income Network (Italy)
CMS	Center for Peace Studies (Croatia)
FBK	Fondazione Bruno Kessler
MdC	Museu da Crise (The Netherlands)
UNITN	University of Trento
VIGs	Visual Identity Guidelines

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1. PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT IN PIE NEWS

Fig. 03

The PIE News project is investing a lot of resources and energy in public engagement with the project itself and, prospectively, with the commonfare.net digital platform. Public engagement in PIE News is based on a pilot-driven strategy: this means that the three pilot actions (in Croatia, Italy, and the Netherlands) are driving the design and implementation of the PIE News project, triggering a public engagement process. The activities of dissemination, exploitation, and communication are to be read in the light of the goal to foster public engagement in relation to the Commonfare concept and the commonfare.net digital platform.

This chapter begins with the public engagement strategy of PIE News as sketched out in the Grant Agreement signed with the European Commission and provides the rationale for the strategy that has been implemented. This is based on the envisioned strategy, but adapted to the results coming from work done with the population PIE News is intended to support precarious workers, welfare recipients, and people not in education, employment, or training.

1.1 PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT AS PART OF THE DESIGN AND SUSTAINABILITY STRATEGY

PIE News capitalizes on the collective power and skills of the 'new poor,' promoting Commonfare through actions that increase collective awareness about PIE Conditions and promote engagement with both the concept of Commonfare, the innovative welfare model the project is fostering, and the digital platform commonfare.net. In this context, we can theoretically read the dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities as part of the public design process the project is enacting: dissemination and communication are ways to establish attachments between people and the project, while exploitation is a way toward granting the appropriation of the Commonfare concept and digital platform by relevant social actors.

As reported in the grant agreement, task 5.2, public

engagement, "is dedicated to support the relationship with WP2 pilots and WP4 platform and thus disseminating the project by: 1) further expanding the PIE public facilitating the engagement of new citizens and sector specific organisations; 2) attracting policy makers and other stakeholders; 3) reaching out for the scientific community. Besides coordinating the dissemination efforts with WP2 dissemination workshops and WP4 platform, task 5.2 ensures the participation of PIE News partners to external events and publications, as well as the timely publication of all public deliverables on the platform".

The connection with WP2, Pilot Actions, is a key component, as the population involved in pilot actions is the first reference point for the dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities carried on by the Consortium. PIE News piloting activities constitute in fact the first strategy implemented to provide capabilities to be effective storytellers and to successfully promote the circulation of digital currencies in order to make Commonfare a sustainable model. In the light of WP5 tasks (focus of this documents), and T5.2 in particular, the first half of the project has been mainly devoted to dissemination and communication while the exploitation activities will increase during the second half of the project, in particular through the PIE News Networking Events. All these activities rely on the nine letters of support that accompanied the submitted proposal. These letters anticipated a potential audience of up to one hundred thousand people, and they were mainly rooted in the networks of the pilot partners (BIN Italy, Center for Peace Studies, and Museu da Crise).

The empirical activities conducted during WP2 (see D2.1), as well as an unanticipated Early User Survey (described extensively in D5.1) and the analysis of engagement with the Commonfare Facebook page, have pointed to the need of revising the communication and dissemination strategy described in Section 2.2 of the Grant Agreement (page 149 - 158), based on three main findings: 1) the rejection, by the population PIE News is working with, of the institutionalized forms of labelling, like the categories of "at risk of poverty and social exclusion" (D2.1); 2) adjustments to the technologies

actually used by the same population, in order to maximise the reach; and 3) the centrality of offline relations in driving everyday practices by the same population. These three findings have been central in refining the original plan and the remainder of this document accounts for the activities carried out in the light of the aforementioned empirical findings.

1.2 REFINING THE ORIGINAL PLAN TO ADAPT TO FIELDWORK AND EMPIRICAL CONSTRAINTS

Three factors pushed toward refining the original plan, both in terms of the timing of the use of some communication tools (e.g. the newsletter) and of the language. The most visible of these changes deals with the public name of the project, PIE News. The project team encountered resistance related to the unfolding of the acronym in terms of poverty, lack of income, and unemployment, and the name was widely rejected by participants in empirical activities conducted during WP2 research (see D2.1). Therefore, since February 2017, the project's public identity has been branded as Commonfare and not PIE News (see Figure 1 for the two logos).

This was the biggest change in the project dissemination, communication, and exploitation strategy. In addition, other changes took place that reflect a set of principles that emerged more and more clearly while the empirical activities were proceeding. The principles we are adhering to are the following:

- ▶ adopt an inclusive language;
- ▶ reuse well-crafted content through different channels;
- ▶ maximise the capacity to build offline connections.

As anticipated, the need for an inclusive language originates in the rejection of institutional language by the population we encountered in the empirical work conducted during WP2 and that has been described by Bassetti et al. (2017). The principle of strategic reuse, where content is adapted for each of the different communication channels used such as factsheets, the Facebook page, the newsletter, and the commonfare.net digital platform, satisfies the need for high-quality and cost-effective communication. Facebook was chosen as the main social media platform because the aforementioned Early User Survey showed how, among the 132 respondents, 96 declared they use Facebook regularly, while all the other social media considered (Twitter, LinkedIn, Snapchat, Instagram) are used frequently by a very low percentage of respondents. It should be noted how the respondents were recruited through emails, Twitter accounts, and Facebook profiles, and that suggests that, even in case of self-selection in the response rate, Facebook appears as the social media most likely to engage people. The principle of maximising offline relations is also a consequence of empirical findings reported in D2.1, as social relations were suggested as crucial to supporting people in the absence of institutionalized welfare. They have therefore

Figure 4. The PIE News and Commonfare logos

become a central part of the Commonfare project approach. This suggests that good quality communication content is also produced through face-to-face interactions among the consortium partners and different audiences (in the pilot sites, in academic venues, or public presentations), and that communication is oriented toward promoting face-to-face events and encounters between pilot organizations and local populations, which take place on daily basis.

From a communication perspective, these three principles relate to and modify the three project goals of informing people about existing welfare provisions, facilitating the sharing of stories about bottom-up welfare good practices, and supporting such initiatives to spread to other contexts as well as to scale. In particular, they suggest seeing communication and dissemination as a way to inform people, support meaning-making, and favour the construction of relations, with all three happening in parallel. These three lenses (detailed in chapter 2) are all part of the process of supporting the emergence of a recursive public, the goal of public design, in which a recursive public is a social aggregate caring for the condition of its own existence (Kelty, 2008; Teli et al., 2015). Having information, collectively engaging in sense-making, and building relations are all elements necessary to foster the emergence of a recursive public (Botto and Teli, 2017).

1.3 STRATEGIES

The goal to support the emergence of a recursive public implies that the PIE News project should create conditions that allow people to get relevant information, collectively engage in sense-making, and build social relations.

Strategically, that has been achieved - throughout PIE News WP5 - by reading offline and online interactions as part of

relational practices that move between different media, from face-to-face to digitally mediated forms of interaction. In both cases, communication and dissemination reflect both content produced by the project, like events, communication material or scientific articles, and content on the topic of the project produced by wider research networks, NGOs, and individuals. Both kinds of content are visible in digital communications such as the project Facebook page, and face-to-face events such as the events in Milan and Rome (see Section 3).

Convergence between the different communication channels is represented in the working metaphors the consortium has adopted to design, develop, and communicate commonfare.net. The metaphors have been developed through two different internal documents, with the goal to provide the PIE News project with: 1) a strong connection with the field of inquiry and action, maximizing the possibilities for the implemented technologies to be useful for the people involved in the fieldwork activities and for other people in similar social conditions; 2) the capacity to innovate the domain of “collective awareness platforms” going beyond the replication of established patterns of platform design, on the basis of the challenges that the empirical work has brought to established ways of dealing with precarious lives, even linguistically.

Metaphors are bridges between different social worlds and any metaphor “may heal or create, erase or violate, impose a voice or embody more than one voice” (Star, 1991). Metaphors should, therefore, be taken seriously, especially in their immediate implications. As the goal of PIE News is to support the part of the European population that is financially struggling and, at the same time, experimenting with bottom-up initiatives, we have envisioned two main metaphors, each building upon the other: first, we foresee our activities as part of a collaborative ecology of tools for autonomous, practicable, and poetic lives, stressing people’s autonomy, everyday improvement in their life, and beauty in all of that; second, we articulate the ecology from a design perspective through the metaphor of a rhizome, referring to, and paraphrasing Deleuze and Guattari (1987), a form that challenges hierarchical organizational structures, ceaselessly establishing connection between social life, discourses, and power, or, said in other ways, a rhizome is always in the middle, drawing upon and establishing relations. These two parallel and dialogically established metaphors point to the overarching goal of communication, dissemination, and exploitation practices in PIE News, building relations. The following sections articulate how this has been achieved so far, and how it will be achieved in the future, in the context of the project activities.

2. COMMUNICATION

Fig. 05

Communication is a key component of the PIE News project. In fact questions of communication and language are central to the project activities (both field research and design) given the dissatisfaction with and resistance to the institutional lexicon mentioned in the previous section. These difficulties led the consortium to realize that the language which had been used to present the original project ideas to funding agencies was not congruent with, and even undermined, the aims of our research and development activities.

In light of this, the whole consortium engaged in an important process of self-reflexivity with regards to the role of communication in the project, arguing that communication is not just about expression (that is the presentation and the description of the project to an audience). Rather, it is mainly a collection of frames (Goffman, 1974) – specific fields of meaning that organize and give sense to events around us – which help structure how meanings and messages are presented to an audience, with the purpose to influence the choices people make about how to process that information. As a consequence, communication in PIE News has been understood and developed according to three main trajectories:

- ▶ communication as informing;
- ▶ communication as meaning-making;
- ▶ communication as relation.

In what follows, we describe these three trajectories and aims.

2.1 AIMS

2.1.1 Informing

Understanding communication as informing highlights the transmission of information in order to make the recipient aware of something: informing people about welfare provision, a meeting with stakeholders that is going to take place somewhere, an upcoming publication on the

project, etc. Some words defining this instance are: initiator, recipient, information, dissemination, and message. Here are two examples of information delivered through communication in the project:

1. (from Commonfare Facebook page - April 21, 2017):

Today we are happy to present and discuss #Commonfare at #CommonFareTrentino, a round table that aims to connect ideas and projects about the management of common goods emerging from the urban development planning of Trentino (an autonomous province in the north of Italy) with experiences and values that nurture Commonfare. This is one of the many public events we are planning in order to raise awareness among public institutions and local stakeholders with regard to our project and the goals that drive its actions.

<https://www.facebook.com/Commonfare/photos/a.1792405231023043.1073741830.1743335312596702/1853369634926602/?type=3&theater>

2. (from a design workshop exercise on writing a Facebook post, taking place in Zagreb, January 2017):

Thanks to a local agreement between “Banca del Tempo” and “Kaleidoscopio” in Trento, Commonfare.net participants that are involved in “time bank” can earn “pies” [digital coins] also helping people through ICT support.

These two examples show what communication as informing is mainly about, that is transmission of information in order to make the recipient aware of something: informing people about welfare provision or a meeting with stakeholders that is going to take place somewhere.

2.1.2 Meaning-making

Communication as meaning-making refers to communication as an interpretative process in which a subject seeks to understand the intentions and interactional moves of the other through the signs whereby they are displayed. This mode of communication is embodied in some artifacts such as posters, flyers, stickers, etc. Some words that define this mode are: visuals (colors, shapes,

lines), meanings, sense, comprehension, interpretation, meaning-making, sense-making, meaning-breaking, and self-presentation (Goffman, 1974). Here are two examples of communication as meaning-making undertaken in the project:

1. (from project's flyer - April 2017):

Around 25% of people living in Europe are precarious workers, people unprotected by safety nets, and young people who are no longer in the education system, who face difficulties finding a job. Despite our troubles, many of us collaborate with each other as equals, freely experiment with novel ways of living, and express solidarity in our daily lives. Collaboration, experimentation, and solidarity are our strengths: Commonfare.net supports them.

2. (from a design workshop exercise on writing a Facebook post, undertaken in Zagreb, January 2017):

In the era of second generation algorithms new platforms offering individual services on welfare spread all around. These platforms generate huge profits for providers and low incomes for those who work on them. #PIENEWS represents an important chance to collectively cooperate and exchange on a cooperative and participatory base.

Communication as meaning-making refers to communication as an interpretative process in which signs – such as words or images – are used not just to transmit information, but to create subjective and collective meanings based on individual and shared experiences. In this case communication becomes a more complex interaction, involving not only what we know during the exchange, but also the system of knowledge, values, beliefs, opinions that belong to us and that intervene in the communications process.

2.1.3 Building relations

This mode entails the idea that communicating means constructing a relation by making something in common, sharing something, participating in something. In this case communicating means becoming involved in a relation that pays attention to the identity and roles of the subjects (e.g. who are the people who participate in this relation? Who is in? Who is left out?) and to the character of the relation itself, which both precedes and takes shape during communication. Words relating to this mode are: consensus, community, participation, reciprocity, trust, care, subjectivity, symbols, and culture. Therefore relation here has a twofold meaning: (1) 'reference to' something and (2) 'bond with something/somebody'. Here are two examples of this more complex understanding of communication in the project:

1. (from a Commonfare Facebook page - October 4, 2017):

This week pilot partner Museu da Crise was invited to present #Commonfare during a 5 day program at the Tijdelijk Museum

that serves as a prelude to the Carnival of Oppressed Feelings by the wonderful and inspiring artist Gluklya Pershina. Goal of these 5 sessions is to provide input for the manifesto of the Utopian Unemployment Union of Amsterdam, a project by the same artist. The manifesto will be presented during the Carnival...

<https://www.facebook.com/Commonfare/posts/1927004940896404>

2. (from from a Commonfare Facebook event - September 28, 2017):

We are very proud and excited to organize a public event to present and discuss #Commonfare with other four European projects focused on social innovation. The event will be hosted by the City of Milan, with the participation of Cristina Tajani (City Councillor for Employment Policies) and Pierfrancesco Majorino (City Councillor for Social Policies)...

<https://www.facebook.com/Commonfare/photos/a.1792405231023043.1073741830.1743335312596702/1924554164474815/?type=3&theater>

2.2 GUIDELINES

To build an effective and recognizable communication identity requires the alignment of the project's practices, goals, and values with the empirical data we are able to collect (some discussed in this document, others discussed in D2.1, D3.1 and D3.2). In practice, this means that the three trajectories described above (informing, exchanging meaning, and building relations) should be aligned as much as possible. This in turn means that the content of our communication (what we say) should be coherent with a particular and recognizable form (how we say something). A mismatch between the content and form of communication might explain, for example, the rejection of the original institutional language (made up by words such as 'user', 'stakeholder', 'PIE', 'poor') by participants in pilot activities aimed at engaging potential commoners.

In order to address these challenges and pursue a more effective public engagement strategy, the consortium has developed some guidelines aiming at promoting a more inclusive language, reflecting a fundamentally inclusive attitude throughout the project's thinking.

2.2.1 Constructing and promoting an inclusive communication

As suggested in the previous section, these guidelines have been developed to build up and employ a collective language that is as sensitive as possible to the people we are working with. In general, we can say that the language (written, oral, visual) that nurtures our communication activities should aim to avoid stereotypes and exclusion relating to gender, race, class, age, religion, ableness, education, technical

literacy and so on. In this respect, it is important to keep in mind that the use and perception of language is highly contextual and culturally-dependent, so what might be an acceptable phrase (e.g. ‘the elderly’) for one context can be experienced differently in another context. What follows are some examples and suggestions that illustrate our approach, mostly focused on non-sexist language.

2.2.2 Adopting a non-discriminatory language

What follows are practical examples of a non-discriminatory language that the communication team has developed and shared with the whole consortium. These examples are written in English, but are to be translated and/or adapted (when possible) to the relevant local language.

► Use the plural form for both nouns and pronouns

EXAMPLE WITH BIAS

“Each person should support Commonfare regardless **his** level of income”

EXAMPLE WITH BIAS REMOVED

“All persons should support Commonfare regardless **their** level of income”

► Use neutral nouns

EXAMPLE WITH BIAS

“We would like to thank the municipality **spokesman** attending this meeting”

EXAMPLE WITH BIAS REMOVED

“We would like to thank the municipality **spokespersons** attending this meeting”

► Including both genders in order to make female referent visible

EXAMPLE WITH BIAS

“Each welfare recipient must submit **his** request to local agencies”

EXAMPLE WITH BIAS REMOVED

“Each welfare recipient must submit **his/her** request to local agencies”

► Avoid reinforcing heteronormativity and gender binarism

Example 1

EXAMPLE WITH BIAS

Margherita and Alessia have full time jobs; they share the housework.

Example 2

EXAMPLE WITHOUT BIAS

Marco is an unemployed free-lancer living in Rome; **she** lives with **her** old friend...

Fig. 06

Vary your choice of pronouns when you want to give examples that emphasize the action of an individual. Ideally, choose pronouns that work counter to prevailing stereotypes (Desprez-Bouanchaud, Doolaage, Ruprecht, and Pavlic, 1999):

▶ **To counter the stereotype that women are not tech-savvy whereas men are:**

Example 1

EXAMPLE WITH BIAS

Our lost and challenged participant is not alone in understanding how to navigate Commonfare.net. **Her** difficulties in gaining a comprehensive understanding are shared by a large group of people.

EXAMPLE WITH BIAS REMOVED

Our lost and challenged participant is not alone in understanding how to navigate Commonfare.net. **His** difficulties in gaining a comprehensive understanding are shared by a large group of people.

Example 2

EXAMPLE WITH BIAS

A **hacker** is not a person who breaks into or otherwise violates the system integrity of remote machines with malicious intent, but **he** constantly seeks further knowledge, freely share what **he** has discovered, and never intentionally damage data.

EXAMPLE WITH BIAS REMOVED

A **hacker** is not a person who breaks into or otherwise violates the system integrity of remote machines with malicious intent, but **she** constantly seeks further knowledge, freely share what **she** has discovered, and never intentionally damage data.

▶ **To avoid reinforcing gender-based division of labor**

Example 1

EXAMPLE WITH BIAS

Recent research points out that **engineering workers** often neglect their **wives** and children.

EXAMPLE WITH BIAS REMOVED

Recent research points out that **engineering workers** often neglect their **families**.

Example 2

EXAMPLE WITH BIAS

Carl and Joan both have full time jobs; **he helps her** with the housework

EXAMPLE WITH BIAS REMOVED

Carl and Joan both have full time jobs; **they share** the housework

▶ **Use more neutral nouns. Some examples:**

TRADITIONAL

user

ALTERNATIVE

participants; people

stakeholder

institutional partner; institutional actor, intermediaries

poor

people experiencing critical conditions, people 'having a tough time'

man

individual; women and men, person

mankind

humanity, human kind, humans,

mothertongue

first language

fatherland

homeland

manpower

workforce

2.2.3 Beyond language: building an inclusive context

On a more general level, looking at contextual aspects beyond pattern of language, the communication team has advanced some reflections about the importance of fostering diverse and inclusive participation in design workshops and public events organized mostly in the pilot countries. Drawing upon the recommendations of like-minded projects and cooperatives working on strengthening movements for social justice and a solidarity economy (e.g. www.aorta.coop), the consortium is focusing on developing participation, especially among people from socially marginalized groups. This concern focuses, for example, on the risks of social exclusion for non-Western migrants, women, trans and gender non-conforming people, poor people, disabled people, who might not be always able to recognize and appreciate their own skills as a consequence of the internalization of values prescribed by white supremacy, patriarchy, capitalism, and ableism.

In practice, fostering inclusive participation means paying attention to the kinds of people and behavior present during a workshop or meeting, in order to encourage participation not only by people who feel comfortable or entitled to leadership positions, but also by those who might feel not so comfortable in speaking up and, accordingly, might run the risk of staying at the margins.

2.3 TOOLBOX

PIE News can count on a diverse set of communication tools that serve multiple purposes. Tools available for external communication activities include: the project website (pieproject.eu), our Facebook page (www.facebook.com/Commonfare/), newsletters, flyers, posters, stickers, factsheets, press releases, deliverables, and publications. The commonfare.net digital platform itself is also becoming more and more central to the project communication and dissemination strategy.

The list of tools above comprises both textual forms (such as press releases, factsheets) and media forms (such as the website and the Facebook page), a distinction that could be useful in order to understand the different forms of communication that these tools enable. For example, press releases, publications (e.g. papers, books), and deliverables mostly consist of closed narratives made up of written verbal text, with a finite number of authors, performing a top-down form of communication. The newsletter resembles press releases, publications, and deliverables in terms of being a written text, but it can become a multimedia text with the presence of links that connect to other textual forms such as video or audio tracks. Posters, factsheets, stickers, and flyers are syncretic texts in that they combine different languages and expressive forms such as images and words, which follow a coherent and strategic expressive line.

The website and the Facebook page are media forms comprising different kinds of text, languages and formats, organized through specific rules, conventions, channels (e.g. posts, comments, etc...), and technical configurations.

In PIE News, the website and the Facebook page promote two different processes of communication in a strategic manner: the website provides information and updates about the project without enabling interaction, whereas the purpose of the Facebook page is to spread information about the project and to deliver other content related to the project (e.g. critical analysis, trailers, news, etc.), which may add sense to the activities and goals of the project.

Along with these media tools, we should not forget that physical presence and ordinary encounters are also powerful means whereby to cultivate public engagement and the formation of a recursive public around the digital platform commonfare.net and the value of Commonfare itself. The physical presence of pilot partners in local sites has resulted, for example, in the opening of the first two so-called CommonKiosks in Rotterdam and The Hague (places where people can meet and openly as well as privately talk about the issues they face in daily life) and in the growing connections with local communities based in Croatian islands.

The communication tools so far described serve the main goals of communication in PIE News, that is informing about activities and events, disseminating results to multiple audiences contributing to shared meaning-making, and building relations able to foster public engagement.

2.3.1 Website

The PIE News project website (pieproject.eu) is the main communication channel acting as an informing hub, thus featuring all relevant information about the project and related topics (project objectives, information, news, event announcements, public reports, analysis, links to related initiatives). The website has been developed with a very user-friendly interface, in which a brief, overall description of the project is visible and accessible at first sight, along with the main sections (“News”, “Our goals”, “Timeline”, “Resources”, “Contacts”, “Partners”).

The section “News” contains updates regarding the project, including events, new publications published and press outputs covering the project; according to the planned dissemination strategy, starting from Fall 2017 all the news on the project website is shared on the Facebook page so as to increase the amount of traffic on the website and to favour cross-communication between the website and the Facebook page.

Another important part of the website is the section “Resources”, wherein all the project publications, deliverables, info materials and multimedia are stored. This section constitutes a sort of library, with all project-related documents available so as to make the results of the project accessible to the public at large.

According to the analytics regularly analysed in order to improve this website’s efficiency, the website performance shows a clear positive trend during nearly one year of activity, as the following table points out:

METRICS	01/09/2016 – 30/11/2016 (3M)	01/12/2016 – 28/02/2017 (3M)	01/03/2017 – 30/06/ 2017 (4M)	01/07/2017 – 30/09/2017 (3M)	01/10/2017 – 18/12/2017 (2-3M)
Sessions	694	891	1,211	672	1,003
Users	374	492	751	406	704
Pages viewed	1,374	1,833	2,023	1,199	1,704
Bounce rate	42,36%	59,60%	71,92%	71,88%	71,78%

Table 1. Website analytics

As this table shows, the website performance registered a rather clear improvement between the first six months of the project activities (from September 2016 and early 2017) and the year 2017 until October, as indicated by the number of sessions and users. According to the website analytics, such improvement is due to three main interrelated factors: the publication of project deliverables (especially D2.1 and D3.1), the organization of offline events which brought new audiences to the website, and the related publication of news, which has been shared on the Facebook page. The advertisement of specific content on the website through other channels, such as the Facebook page, may also explain the highest bounce rate, as people have reached the project website to read or access specific content, and not with a general curiosity about the project. The high bounce rate could also be related to the existence of another website with an almost identical url (pienews.com) to the project's one.

2.3.2 Facebook Page

Together with the project website, the official Facebook page plays an important role within project communication. The Facebook page was set up at the beginning of the project so as to increase the project outreach in collaboration with the existing channels of partners and supporting organisations. The main goal of the Facebook page is that of spreading information about the project (e.g. upcoming events, new publications, research outputs), but also delivering other content (e.g. critical analysis, trailers, news, etc.) related to the goals of the project, so that to foster participation and engagement.

Since the beginning of the project's social media activities, the Facebook page has registered a growing and promising rate of total likes, reach and engagement, as the following tables shows:

January 10, 2017	175
June 19, 2017	546
December 7, 2017	1031

Table 2. Facebook analytics - Total likes

December 1, 2016 – January 1, 2017	3048
October 31, 2017 – November 29, 2017	7003

Table 3. Facebook analytics - Total reach average (unique users)¹

December 1, 2016 – January 1, 2017	227
October 31, 2017 – November 29, 2017	617

Table 4. Facebook analytics - Engaged users average (unique users)²

The positive trend indicated by public engagement with the Facebook page appears to relate to two interconnected activities: the organization of public events in the pilot countries, which gathered a significant numbers of participants, and the increasing variety of content and format (such as the Facebook dissemination cards) available on the Facebook page. As an example of the former, an increase rate of total likes of the project Facebook page occurred during October 2017, when pilot partners BIN Italia and Museu da Crise engaged in the organization of public events to

increase the project's visibility. In relation to the latter, the communication team has focused on publishing a variety of content on the Facebook page, with the goal to reach as many publics as possible. Other than sharing hyperlinks to relevant pieces of information or events, the strategy to spread both content deriving from project research outputs and content drawn upon the project-related literature has been strengthened through the design of project-based Facebook dissemination cards, as in the two examples below:

¹The number of people who have seen any content associated with the page (Unique Users).

²The number of people who engaged with the page. Engagement includes any click or story created (Unique Users).

Figure 7. Facebook dissemination card (quote from a founding figure in the field of Participatory Design)

2.3.3 Newsletter

One of the project communication and dissemination tools is the newsletter. The newsletter has been released later than originally planned in order to adjust to the needs of the relations cultivated during the pilot actions. In particular, the incremental character of such relations suggested to refrain from creating content that did not have an audience yet, and the newsletter was also not pushed as an exclusively digital form of communication. In fact, the Consortium agreed to wait for the availability of rich research material and public events to be communicated. It has also kept subscription as simple as possible, using a button on the project website, in the hope of reaching a wider audience beyond those engaged in social research.

The first newsletter was sent out on November 18, 2017 to 56 subscribers (10 of which are project members) through MailChimp, a professional emailing solution chosen to ensure the best delivery rate. According to MailChimp analytics, the rate of successful deliveries is 56 (100%), with a total opens (total number of times the campaign was opened by recipients, considering multiple opens from individual recipients) of 51 and an open rate (percentage of total recipients who opened the campaign) of 39,3%: this can be considered a successful outcome if we take into account that, according to Mailchimp's analysis, the average open rate in the category 'Social Networks and Online Communities' is 21,71%³. The first issue of the PIE News newsletter is available at the following link: <http://mailchimp/935d0dd681a0/commonfare-newsletter-1>

As far as content is concerned, the newsletter aims to cover multiple aspects of the project: field research, pilot activities, design of the platform, events, and research outputs. Four main sections have been developed for the newsletter to address these aspects: "voices from the field", "events", "commonfare.net in the spotlight" and "the academic corner".

Future issues of the newsletter will include these four sections, with all the members of the consortium (pilots, researchers, technical partners) contributing to the development of content.

Figure 8. Facebook dissemination card (quote from D2.1 Research Report)

2.3.4 Flyers, posters, stickers

As indicated in the grant agreement, flyers, posters and stickers have been designed in English and translated in the pilot languages (Croatian, Dutch, Italian) to be used and delivered at events that the PIE News consortium have organised or contributed to.

Due to the significant change in terms of language explained in Section 1.2, the early flyers, posters and stickers - developed after the project Kick-Off Meeting and available in print for the first design workshop (September 2016) - have been replaced with new ones, which include the different logo (from PIE News to Commonfare) and a slightly different graphic arrangement.

Figure 9. Poster used during a networking event in Milan

³Data updates to February 1, 2017. <https://mailchimp.com/resources/research/email-marketing-benchmarks/>

The main goal behind the use of flyers, posters and stickers is that of disseminating information and constructing meanings about the project to different publics during offline events. In this respect, these tools serve as a first clue to the project, helping to bring people to richer communication platforms such as the Facebook page and the website.

2.3.5 Factsheets

As of now, two factsheets have been produced in English to promote PIE News key data, concepts and messages by means of appealing infographics to be distributed on the Web (social media, communities, partners' networks, external blogs). The first factsheet introduces the social context in which the project is situated through quantitative data regarding precarious conditions in Europe, with a focus on the three pilot countries.

The second factsheet features the major findings from the socio-economic analysis and qualitative research carried out by pilot partners in Croatia, Italy, and The Netherlands, and illustrated in deliverable D2.1 "Research report". The main components of the second factsheet are in fact some key information about the history and the current configuration of welfare systems in the three countries; a description of the emerging needs manifested by research participants; and examples of bottom-up welfare good practices, including the criteria used by pilot partners to identify them. As stated in the grant agreement, the factsheet has been disseminated mainly through online channels in order to keep the project's ecological footprint as low as possible. According to the website analytics, the data related to the first factsheet amount to 41 total pageviews and 34

DATE	FLYERS	POSTERS	STICKERS
September 2016	7.000	/	5.000
October 2016 ⁴	3.500	/	/
April 2017	6.000	43	2.000

Table 5. Number of flyers, posters, stickers printed

unique pageviews. This factsheet has also been printed to be distributed during significant events organized by pilot partners. The final draft of the second factsheet was presented and approved during the last general assembly (December 2017), and we anticipate its online publication by mid-January.

2.3.6 Press releases

Press releases are communication formats that are usually prepared in conjunction with important events organized by the consortium. They are sent to targeted media outlets in order to achieve press coverage and disseminate the project and its activities. For example, in the case of two recent events organized in Milan in October 2017 (see Table 7), press releases have been successfully sent to local media, resulting in interesting press outputs (see publications table).

Furthermore, as declared in the grant agreement, efforts to advertise project events and activities are carried out in synergy with the EC communication channels such as the CAPSSI website (www.capssi.eu), whose section "News" have welcomed some updates about PIE News events, and coordination with ChiC, the Coordination and Support Action aiming at amplifying and coordinating the efforts of CAPSSI projects.

WEBSITE ANALYTICS				FACEBOOK ANALYTICS			FLYERS	POSTERS	STICKERS	
Sessions	Users	Pages Viewed	Bounce rate	Total likes	Total reach average	Engaged users average	Total	Total	Total	
01/09/2016				10/01/2017			09/2016	7000	5000	
694	374	1374	42%	175						
(3M)										
01/12/2016				19/06/2017			10/2016⁴	3500		
891	492	1833	60%	546						
(3M)										
01/03/2017				07/12/2017			10/2017	6000	43	2000
1211	751	2023	72%	1031						
(4M)										
01/07/2017				01/12/2016						
672	406	1199	72%		3048	227				
(3M)				01/01/2017						
				31/10/2017						
				29/11/2017						

Table 6. Overview of media analytics

⁴ This printing was made only for Croatia and The Netherlands due to wrong translations in the first version of September 2016.

2.4 PLAN OF COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

2.4.1 Integrating different tools: constructing media ecology

The diverse set of communication tools described above serves to shape a ‘media ecology’ (Fuller, 2005) in which each tool and medium is used according to its particular characteristics in order to convey targeted messages to diverse publics (policy-makers, stakeholders, participants, press, general audience, scientific community). For example, a content shared on Facebook is shown to a different audience from the one identified by a press release. This differentiation is due both to the structural configuration of the medium and the tool and, accordingly, to the the different rationale whereby they are employed. The concept of media ecology (see Fuller, 2005) recalls the idea of ‘environment’ as well as complex and simultaneous interactions of media systems, which, as such, are not technological tools conveying messages, but rather cultural, technical, and communicative forms in which people live and interact.

In order to foster public engagement around the project, the communication team has thus developed some general action to be undertaken, following a twofold rationale:

1. to disseminate the content we create through our research activities (our content);
2. to enrich our content, research, and actions by getting in touch with other content (research projects, social and political initiatives, critical analysis, academic scholarship, etc.).

As illustrated in section 2.3.2 concerning the Facebook page, for example, this logic emerges from the development

of two kinds of dissemination cards, with red ones used to disseminate our own content, and green ones deployed to disseminate “other content”.

2.4.2 Communicating bottom-up welfare practices: similarities and potential collaboration

In planning public engagement activities, the communication team has devoted particular attention to the dissemination of information regarding bottom-up welfare “good practices” reported by pilot organizations in D2.1. These good practices constitute examples of real-world enactment and application of Commonfare according to the criteria identified by pilot organizations, so it is important to communicate them in the most effective way, and to connect them in order to scale up beyond the three pilot countries.

Against this backdrop, the communication team has worked to provide an open map of good practices (see Figure 5), which are connected through two types of link that aim to trace out similarities and potential collaboration. Starting from the acknowledgement that connections among good practices are multiple, and certainly more than those highlighted in the following visualization, the purpose of the map is that of drawing relations among different experiences that are yet bounded by some of the keywords conveyed by the concept of ‘Commonfare’ as emerged from D2.1: ‘economy of us’, ‘social mutualism’, ‘bottom-up welfare’, ‘conviviality’, ‘platform cooperativism’, mutual-aid’, ‘communal living’, ‘critical thinking’, ‘shared responsibility’ and others. Such ‘bottom-up welfare experiments’ are then organized according to the concept of ‘commoning’. As the progressive form of the verb suggests, ‘commoning’ points to a process of communalizing material means of production and reproduction, practices, and goals. This appears as a primary mechanism in order to create collective interests

Fig. 10

and mutual bonds, build lines of resistance and autonomous spaces, and move beyond abstract solidarity. These goals remind to an ultimate meaning, that is the constitution of good practices as a common subject (=community), that 'has to be intended not as a gated reality, a grouping of people joined by exclusive interests separating them from others, as with communities formed on the basis of religion or ethnicity, but rather as a quality of relations, a principle

of cooperation and of responsibility to each other and to the earth, the forests, the seas, the animals" (Federici, 2011). The overall process of 'commoning' is therefore defined by three main dynamics: experimentation, coalition building, reparation and maintenance. These three dynamics seem to characterize the bottom-up welfare practices introduced in D2.1, and so they also inform the nature of the links whereby they are connected.

Figure 11. Map of bottom-up welfare good practices

The links of 'similarities' and 'potential collaboration' have been identified on the basis of one the main goals of the project, that is networking. The plan is to communicate and disseminate bottom-up welfare good practices from Croatia, Italy and The Netherlands through the platform to leverage network effects and the collaborative co-creation of solutions exemplified by these promising experiences to cope with difficulties in everyday life.

With these premises, fostering the construction of connections of good practices according to the link of 'similarities' will mean, for example, connecting an experiment in critical consumption in Italy to a similar

experiment based in Croatia; on the other hand, connecting good practices following the link of 'potential collaboration' could mean, for example, leveraging on the resources and proactivity coming from a coffee bar in Rotterdam that exclusively works with young people who have been in prison providing them with training and jobs and connect it with a community-based and self-organised gym in Rome. Such a connection aims to allow good practices focused on different themes and issue to exchange and integrate organizational practices, strategies to relate with institutional actors, and plans to ensure sustainability.

3. EVENTS

Fig. 12

3.1 AIMS

As anticipated, the main goals of organizing events in the context of the PIE News project is to foster face-to-face encounters while promoting the project, the commonfare.net digital platform, and the concept of 'Commonfare' itself. In particular, in the context of a public design approach, events allow for the establishment of attachments based on commitment to the project, and promote the formation of relations that favour the emergence of a recursive public. To achieve this overarching goal, members of the Consortium have participated to events organized by others (see Section 3.2), like conferences or dissemination activities, and they have engaged in organizing events of their own, the most

relevant ones being the PIE News Networking Events, described in Section 3.3. Especially in the events organized by the Consortium, a particular focus has been (and will be) on involving the bottom-up welfare practices listed in D2.1 in order to strengthen their visibility. There has also been a focus on getting in touch with local stakeholders, like municipalities, trade unions, etc... This last strategy is necessary to promote the formation of the recursive public essential for the lived enactment of Commonfare.

The two following sections list the events the Consortium has participated to, providing a picture of the widespread reach in terms of audiences, from academic to professional, passing through the general public.

3.2 PANEL DISCUSSIONS, FORMAL PRESENTATIONS, SIDE-EVENTS, WORKSHOPS, AND EXHIBITIONS

N°	TYPE	EVENT	LOCATION AND DATE	PARTNER	AUDIENCES
1	Workshop	Digital Social Innovation Fair	Rome (Italy) February, 1-2 2017	MITI, UNITN, DYNE	policy-makers, researchers, institutional partners
2	Workshop	Computer-Supported Cooperative Work Conference	Portland (USA), February 25-March 1	MITI	researchers, academics
3	Panel discussion	#CommonFare Trentino	Trento (Italy), April 21, 2017	FBK, UNITN, BIN, DYNE	policy-makers, stakeholders, general public
4	Formal presentation	Red ES CTS Lost In Translation? People, Technologies, Practices and Concepts Across Boundaries.	Lisbon (Portugal), June 7-9, 2017	MITI	researchers, academics
5	Workshop	Communities & Technologies 2017 – Technology for the Common Good	Troyes (France), June 26-30, 2017	MITI, ABERTAY	researchers, academics
6	Information Kiosk	OltreEconomia Festival 2017 (OEF 2017)	Trento (Italy), May 31 - June 4, 2017	FBK	general public

N°	TYPE	EVENT	LOCATION AND DATE	PARTNER	AUDIENCES
7	Side event	Promoting Commonfare	Amsterdam (The Netherlands), June 23, 2017	DYNE, MdC, MITI, BIN, UNITN	general public, researchers
8	Formal presentation	13th European Sociological Association Conference	Athens (Greece), August 29 - September 1, 2017	MITI/UNITN	researchers; academics
9	Formal presentation	12th Annual International Ethnography Symposium	Manchester (UK), August 29 - September 1, 2017	UNITN, MITI, BIN, ABERTAY	researchers, academics
10	Formal presentation	Decent work, Equity and Inclusion. Passwords for the present and the future	Padua (Italy), October 5-7 2017	UNITN	researchers, academics
11	Formal presentation	Manifest voor een eerlijk armoedebeleid	Rotterdam (Netherlands), October 17, 2017	MdC	local politicians, welfare recipients, institutional partners
12	Formal presentation	Prelude to the Carnival of Oppressed Feelings	Amsterdam (Netherlands), 2 - 6 October, 2017	MdC	politicians, cultural workers, asylum seekers
13	Formal presentation	Discussie VI: Global Currency	Antwerp (Netherlands), October 26, 2017	MdC	cultural workers, freelancers, precarious workers

Table 7. External events

3.3 NETWORKING EVENTS

The organization of networking events is part of the general dissemination strategy and the list of subcontractors for the events constitutes milestone 9. This milestone is slightly delayed as the Consortium is acting in a way that is providing flexibility and potentially higher outreach. The Table 8 includes 19 out of the 24 planned events.

Networking events aim to promote Commonfare and its goals throughout Europe and to recruit new participants to the platform, as well as connecting with stakeholders, and the slight delay in platform design accounted for in WP4 is one of the reasons the Consortium has adjusted the timing of PIE News Networking events. Pilot partners are in charge

of identifying specific subcontractors (citizen organization, associations, NGOs, etc.) for the organization of the events, according to criteria that have been agreed upon by the Consortium, in particular: 1) the different kind of audiences the events could intercept and their potential breadth; 2) geographical coverage of different countries, taking as a starting point the division between Southern Europe (in charge of BIN Italy), Northern Europe (Museu da Crise), and Eastern Europe (Center for Peace Studies); 3) contents that can be generated before or during the event and that can be uploaded to commonfare.net; 4) contribution to the construction of networks possibly contributing to the sustainability of the platform; 5) capacity to give visibility to bottom-up welfare practices in the local context.

PARTNER	SUBCONTRACTORS	EVENT FORMAT	LOCATION	DATE	TARGET AUDIENCE	STRATEGY TO PROMOTE COMMONFARE
BIN	Basic Income Association Portugal	Public lecture on Commonfare	Lisbon	September 25-27, 2017	Policy makers, academic researchers and activists	Presentation Commonfare.net project inside Basic Income Earth Network
BIN	Associazione Studi del Presente	Public presentation of Commonfare.net project	Milan	October 4, 2017	Policy makers, stakeholders	Institutional presentation of Commonfare.net project to the Municipality of Milano
BIN	Associazione Studi del Presente	Conference about Commonfare and social cooperation	Milan	October 29-30, 2017	Activists, grassroots association and good practices	Presentation of Commonfare Community to Italian social movements and best practices in Milano
BIN	Associazione Mompracem	Public presentation of Commonfare.net project	Rome	November 9, 2017	Stakeholders, civil society and activists	Presentation of Commonfare.net project to national network in Rome

PARTNER	SUBCON-TRACTORS	EVENT FORMAT	LOCATION	DATE	TARGET AUDIENCE	STRATEGY TO PROMOTE COMMONFARE
BIN	Rede Renta Basica	Promoting Commonfare.net project	Barcelona	May 2018	Policy makers, civil society and activists	Presentation of Commonfare.net project and best practices examples to open institutional relationship with the Municipality of Barcelona
BIN	Association Solidarity for all	Promoting Commonfare.net project	Athens	September 2018	Civil Society and activists	Presentation of Commonfare.net project and examples of good practices
BIN	Acta / European forum of independent professionals	Promoting Commonfare.net project	Rome	November 2018	Professional workers, free-lancers, stakeholders	Contacts and relationships to implement Commonfare community
CMS	Mreža mladih Hrvatska (Croatian Youth Alliance)	Public debate on increasing precarity of work in Croatia and Europe, the effects on young ppl, social welfare and quality of life, and possible solutions	Zagreb, Croatia	early March, or May 5-10, 2018	policy makers, Ministry of Labour, young people (18-40) interested in alternative philosophies and lifestyles which Subversive FEstival attracts	Promote within the existing Festival promotion materials (if in May), otherwise using big names of presenters (if in March)
CMS	POINT conference Political accountability and technology	Public lecture on Commonfare	Sarajevo, Bosnia	May, 24-28, 2018	young people (18-40) from around Southeast Europe/balkan region, interested in technology for good causes, tech start-ups	TBD
CMS	Media Development Centre	TBD	Sofia, Bulgaria	June 2018	young, NEET, activists, CSOs	TBD
CMS	Southeast European Coalition for the Protection of Whistleblowers	TBD	Bucharest, Romania	November 2018	young, NEET, activists, CSOs	TBD
MdC	Ankommen Saarland	Artistic intervention + conference	Saarbrucken, Germany	TBD	Refugees + policy makers	Working directly with local issues related to welfare and welfare provision to make Commonfare as a concept and commonfare.net the online platform immediately relevant for and applicable to the daily lives of the participants.
MdC	Trade Test Site	Artistic intervention + conference	Aarhus, Denmark	TBD	Precarious women	
MdC	Stirling University	Artistic intervention + conference	Stirling, Scotland	TBD	Students + welfare recipients	
MdC	ExtraCity Kunsthal	Artistic intervention + conference	Antwerp, Belgium	TBD	Freelancers / artists / cultural workers	
MdC	Subtopia	Artistic intervention + conference	Norsborg, Sweden	TBD	Music/theatre/film professionals	
MdC	Dramatikken shus	Artistic intervention + conference	Oslo, Norway	TBD	Feminists + homeless	
MdC	ZAD / LABOFII	Artistic intervention + conference	Notre Dame des Landes, France	TBD	Squatters	
MdC	Rotor	Artistic intervention + conference	Graz, Austria	TBD	Artists + locals	

Table 8. Networking events

4. PUBLICATIONS

Fig. 13

Following the guidelines included in the grant agreement, each partner has focused on the effective dissemination of results deriving from the project fieldwork and events. This dissemination activity has resulted in several different publishing venues in which the project has been presented and discussed. As the following section illustrates, these venues are peer-reviewed journals, magazines, blogs and project deliverables.

The process of dissemination has followed the instructions agreed by the consortium which indicate that a beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give advance notice to the other beneficiaries, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.

4.1 PEER-REVIEWED JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES

Since the beginning of the project, consortium members have made efforts to disseminate findings from their

research on the multiple aspects characterizing the project: socio-economic analysis, design, digital currency, human-computer interaction, meta-research, public engagement, participatory design, political economy.

In terms of publication in peer-reviewed journals, the research and elaboration of such a diverse set of issues has been conducted by researchers engaged in different work packages in collaboration with pilot partners each time the project has had key findings to disseminate. In this respect the project has met and gone beyond the minimum 3 publications planned at M18, with scientific publications that have been submitted and accepted by relevant venues (see Table 9).

On the other hand, magazine and newspaper outputs mostly cover events organized by pilot partners, who, in collaboration with the communication team, got in touch with the local press through a press release about the event in order to solicit media coverage.

NUMBER	ITEM	PARTNER
1	Lyle, P., Sciannamblo M., & Teli, M. (2017) Fostering Commonfare. Infrastructuring Autonomous Social Collaboration. <i>CHI '18 Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems</i> . (Accepted for publication)	MITI
2	Teli, M., De Angeli, A., & Menéndez-Blanco, M. (2017). The positioning cards: on affect, public design, and the common. <i>AI & SOCIETY</i> , 1-8.	MITI/UNITN
3	Lyle, P., Sciannamblo M., & Teli, M. (2017) Fostering Commonfare. Strategies and Tactics in a Collaborative Project. <i>Proceedings of the 29th Australian Computer-Human Interaction Conference</i> .	MITI
4	Botto, F. & Teli, M. (2017). PIE News. A public design project toward commonfare. <i>The Journal of Community Informatics</i> , 13(2), 87-105.	FBK/MITI
5	Botto, F., & Teli, M. (2017). PIE News. A public design project toward Commonfare. <i>Proceedings of the 13th CIRN Conference</i> .	FBK/MITI

Table 9. Journals and Conference Proceedings

NUMBER	DATE	TITLE	PUBLISHER
1	April 21, 2017	#CommonFareTrentino	L'Adige
2	April 21, 2017	"CommonFare", il welfare dal basso	Corriere del Trentino
3	April 21, 2017	Fumagalli: "Il precariato non è irreversibile"	Corriere del Trentino
4	April 22, 2017	Olivi promuove il CommonFare "No al reddito incondizionato"	Corriere del Trentino
5	October 1, 2017	Welfare europeo in crowdsourcing	Nova - Il Sole 24 Ore
6	October 3, 2017	Dalla precarietà al commonfare. Lettura di Rifare il mondo... del lavoro	DeriveApprodi
7	October 4, 2017	Commonfare.net, Una rete digitale nata "dal basso" per il sostegno dei disoccupati	Corriere della Sera - Milano
8	October 4, 2017	Commonfare a Milano	il Manifesto
9	October 28, 2017	Al Macao di Milano il dibattito sulla Cooperazione sociale, l'autodeterminazione e il Commonfare	crudiezone.it
10	November 11, 2017	Il lavoro e il welfare diversi dei precari	Comune.info

Table 10. Newspapers and magazines

The kinds of publication in which the consortium has reported its work responds to the goal stated in the grant agreement to contribute to the general expected impacts set out in the work programme in relation to the topic ICT-10-2015 "Collective Awareness Platforms for Sustainability and Social Innovation". Such expected impacts are defined in terms of distributed approaches, participatory innovation, involvement of citizens, techno-social issues related to key aspects of the networked society, collaboration among citizens, new economic models in general and in the pilot sites. The academic papers so far published and accepted for publication deal with key themes addressed by the PIE News project, such as how to foster social collaboration beyond the local, how to infrastructure autonomous social collaboration, the role of cultural probes in design processes and so on.

On the other hand, media outputs published in magazines have aimed to act at the local level in conjunction with the organization of public events such as round tables, meetings with stakeholders and potential participants. Such media coverage responds to the goal to foster engagement and attachment to the project at the local level, therefore they are almost always connected to the organization of events mostly undertaken by pilot partners.

CAPSSI is an inherently interdisciplinary European research initiative, and as such the PIE News project fully reflects an

interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary ethos by including academic actors, NGOs and technical partners. Therefore, the publications and academic presentations of the project are quite heterogeneous, ranging from design and human-computer interaction journals to the European Sociological Association conference and the Ethnography Symposium. In this respect, our strategy aims to foster public engagement and interest also across different academic communities, as the theme of social innovation is of interest for a diverse set of research areas.

4.2 E-JOURNALS, BLOGS

In addition to peer-reviewed academic journals and magazine outputs, project partners have also contributed to e-Journals and blogs, targeting a larger public with shorter articles and news, as well as to policy oriented publications to enhance PIE News outreach to policy-makers.

Due to the short delay in platform design, the production of media outputs for online platforms such as e-Journals and blogs has slightly slowed. This is to allow the platform design to be accomplished according to the agreed road map, so that pilot partners can advertise commonfare.net in its full capacity on local and international online venues.

NUMBER	DATE	TITLE	WEBSITE
1	October 30, 2017	Un Manifesto per il Commonfare	www.dinamopress.it https://www.dinamopress.it/news/un-manifesto-per-il-commonfare/
2	October 17, 2017	Cooperazione sociale, autodeterminazione, Commonfare	Effimera.org http://effimera.org/cooperazione-sociale-autodeterminazione-commonfare-convegno-effimera-macao-28-29-ottobre-2017/
3	September 20, 2017	Milano 4 ottobre: Commonfare e innovazione sociale	www.bin-italia.org http://www.bin-italia.org/milano-4-ottobre-commonfare-innovazione-sociale/
4	September 17, 2017	Lisbona: 26 settembre reddito di base e Commonfare	www.bin-italia.org http://www.bin-italia.org/lisbona-26-settembre-reddito-base-commonfare/
5	May 30, 2017	Undoing the Ontology of the Poor: A Participatory Design Project	Backchannels - Society for Social Studies of Science http://www.4sonline.org/blog/post/undoing_the_ontology_of_the_poor_a_participatory_design_project
6	January 12, 2017	Crisi del welfare state e welfare del comune: il progetto di ricerca PIE News	Effimera.org http://effimera.org/crisi-del-welfare-state-welfare-del-comune-progetto-ricerca-pie-news-cristina-morini/

Table 11. E-journals, blogs

As mentioned in the previous sections, the goals of publications produced for online platforms such as blogs and e-journals is that of broadening the reach of target audiences, by involving potential stakeholders, policy-makers, potential users, general public, professional press. The rationale behind these media outputs revolves around two main aims: to advertise local events so as to foster public participation from both policy-makers, stakeholders and larger publics, and to publicize commonfare.net so as to foster attachment to the digital platform.

4.3 PROJECT DELIVERABLES

Project public deliverables are also key documents for disseminating PIE News findings: these documents contain a detailed description of the project's findings (and their

wider societal implications) and, once submitted to the EC, they are published online on pieproject.eu, thus making the results of the project accessible to the public at large. These deliverables are available in the website "Library" where other project-related documents are accessible.

Project deliverables are conceived to report all the findings concerning the different aspects of the projects such as data management, socio-economic analysis, evaluation, ethics, communication, user research and scenarios, reputation mechanisms, digital currency and network dynamics. Accordingly, the process of writing these documents is coordinated by each work package leader and then shared within the consortium for internal review. Once the document has been validated by internal reviewers, it is submitted to the EC.

NUMBER	TITLE	DATE
1	D3.2 Reputation Mechanics, Digital Currency Models and Network Dynamics and Algorithms	September 30, 2017
2	D3.1 User Research Report and Scenarios	June 30, 2017
3	D2.1 Research Report	March 31, 2017
4	D1.2 Data Management Plan	December 31, 2016
5	D5.1 Evaluation Plan	November 30, 2016
6	D1.1 Project Handbook	September 30, 2016

Table 12. Deliverables published on the project website

The main purpose of deliverables is that of reporting the development of the project to the European Commission according to the agreed steps and milestones. In this respect, deliverables can be considered essential accountability instruments on which the project is evaluated by funding agencies.

Moreover, as public documents, deliverables play an important role as research materials from which to extract data to be elaborated upon in academic publications and other media outputs.

Another pivotal purpose of the deliverables is that of providing a wealth of findings with which to inform the design of the platform, so as to ensure a genuinely participatory approach not only in the phase of field research and design workshops, but also in the more technical steps of developing the main components of the digital platform.

5. CONCLUSION

Fig. 14

This deliverable has described how PIE News communication and dissemination activities have been undertaken during the first half of the project, characterized by the need to adjust to the results of the empirical research conducted in the pilot sites that led us to adopt an inclusive language and highlighted the centrality of offline relations in lived experiences of the people the PIE News project aims to work with, and hence to the creation and fostering of a Commonfare approach. As stated before, such adaptation has had very significant consequences for the consortium, the most visible one being the change of the public identity from PIE News to Commonfare.

That has also pushed toward producing well-crafted content to be disseminated through different channels, including traditional communication channels, like the project website and a newsletter, and social media channels, in particular Facebook. This is rooted in the results of an Early User Survey that was distributed to respondents reached through the network of existing allies of the Consortium in the first months of the project. The results of this survey suggested that the publics the project seeks to engage use Facebook as their main social media tool, resulting in our emphasis on communication using Facebook.

The combination of the different empirical results has been translated into three principles for communication: adopting an inclusive language; reuse well-crafted content through different channels (Facebook and the commonfare.net platform as the main ones); and maximise the capacity to build offline connections. At a higher level, we have developed an understanding of communication activities as aiming to inform people, promote collective meaning-making, and build relations. The different tools, from the more broadcast ones, like the project website, the newsletter, and the factsheets, to the most interactive ones, like Facebook, have been integrated into a strategy rooted in offline relations and encounters.

From this point of view, the next steps to increase the visibility of the project and people's engagement with it include four strands. One is based on the PIE News Networking Events (see Section 3.3.2 for a list of the nineteen events already planned). A second is based on communication of bottom-up welfare good practices identified in D2.1 (see Section 2.4.2 for a map of relations among them). A third is grounded in the future evolution of the commonfare.net platform itself. This will become increasingly central to our engagement strategy as future releases will include the possibility to create connections as well as tell stories. This will be an important step towards commoners taking ownership and control of the platform, and hence also of communication and engagement within and through it. In order to optimise the chances of this happening in a constructive and timely way, the consortium will adopt a 'train the trainer' logic, according to which pilot partners will undertake workshops and provide online tutorials with key figures within target groups and third party organisations on all the functionalities of the commonfare.net platform. The 'train the trainer' strategy aims to achieve two main goals: (1) to instruct participants in how to use the platform so that they can become "trainers" and take responsibility for the authorship of contents, and (2) to foster the emergence of new "ambassadors" of the project who would be able to involve other participants. This then forms the fourth strand of our future engagement work.

The exposure to more broadcast kind of content, for example via the newsletter or the website, will be driven by face-to-face events situations, but participation in commonfare.net will also be prioritized in these. This approach can be seen in the first issue of the newsletter, which drew on content that had been uploaded to commonfare.net. The goal is, in any case, to converge toward commonfare.net, as soon as WP4 work will reach a sufficient level of maturity, in order to maximise the possibility of the effective formation of a recursive public.

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